

One electron bond - post peer review

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Sent to the author with no reply:

Dear Dr. Shimajiri,

First of all, let me express my sincere appreciation for your work. I was especially impressed that you succeeded in obtaining such a fascinating crystalline structure. I understand that the title of your article itself — *Direct evidence for a carbon–carbon one-electron σ -bond* — emphasizes that the primary goal was to provide direct structural evidence, which fully aligns with the expectations of *Nature*.

That said, I found the synthetic part of the work somewhat brief, which led me to wonder: why was iodine chosen as the oxidant? Did you try other oxidants and find iodine to be the most effective?

For example, it immediately occurred to me that, under the reaction conditions you used, a silver salt might be a promising one-electron oxidant — perhaps something like $\text{Ag}(\text{tol})_3[\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]$. Using such an oxidant might even allow the formation of better crystals or provide additional structural insight.

I would be very grateful for any insights you could share, understanding fully the demands on your time. Once again, congratulations on your remarkable work.

Best regards,

Miloš Večeřa

Independent popularizer of chemistry

Shimajiri, Y.; Ohta, K.; Takamori, R.; Kawamura, Y.; Hasegawa, J.; Ichikawa, T.; ...; Kato, T. Direct Evidence for a Carbon–Carbon One-Electron σ -Bond. *Nature* 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07965-1>

This note was shared as a post-peer review commentary on the Nature article by Shimajiri et al. (2024).